

Built-in resilience: The grassroot coping strategies of SDCA students through pandemic narratives

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Abstract – *This paper explores the significant coping strategies that can be learned from examining how SDCA students are coping with the conditions of transformation as an effect of Covid-19 pandemic. Through the interview conducted with the selected SDCA students coming from Education, Pharmacy, AB Communication, Nursing, and Tourism Management, their stories clearly reflect real life struggles, rooted from the serious effects caused by the Covid-19 pandemic. For most students who are studying in a private school like the SDCA students, it can be assumed that pandemic did not affect them much in terms of financial. The SDCA students although most of them belong to well-off families, also experienced struggle and serious effect, most of them need to work while studying (40%), others sell online (20%), while others were able to create advocacy for them to spend their time meaningfully (20%). Although one student (20%) lost her sister due to Covid-19, but this did not discourage him to stop his studies, but he was able to accept the situation and become fully aware on how to adjust and move on in life by making himself occupied to video streaming. The strong message in this research, however, is that threats, stress, problems or failures exist in all humans, regardless of age or status in life. And through literature, educators can better cultivate the grassroots values of Resilience to prepare students to cope with real life stressing experiences and be able to achieve positive outcomes.*

Keywords: Built-in resilience, grassroot coping strategies, students, pandemic narratives.

To cite this article:

Mosende, K. D. (2021). Built-in resilience: The grassroot coping strategies of SDCA students through pandemic narratives. *SDCA Journal of Education*, 6, 45-48.

Introduction

In this generation of millennials, which problem in mental health is a common issue, how do we prepare students for such real life struggles? According to Jones (2015), Millennials always strive to succeed, but the way this generation was raised have not always taught them to deal with the times when they inevitably fail. As Jones puts it, they have not been allowed to struggle before. They do not have the resilience of previous generations.

For most students who are studying in a private school like the SDCA students, it can be assumed that pandemic did not affect them much in terms of financial. For most of them, it works well when most personalized, and academic resources are sufficiently available. Students from wealthy families who live in cities and some highly urbanized municipalities have more access to generally private and expensive schools, whereas students from low-income families face a lack of classrooms and teachers, as well as nearly inaccessible public schools with limited resources that teachers are often forced to provide (Teodoro, 2020).

However, despite having parents or guardian who can send them to expensive schools, SDCA students also experienced struggles during the pandemic. The grassroots coping strategies that makes the SDCA students survive the life threatening effects of Covid-19 pandemic is very significant. This kind of strategy or philosophy rooted from the Filipino values system, is one thing, especially millennials, should learn from this research.

This paper explores the significant coping strategy that can be learned from examining how SDCA students are coping with the conditions of transformation as an effect of Covid-19 pandemic. It seeks to answer the following questions: 1) What challenges related to Covid-19 pandemic that SDCA students need to cope with? 2) How do these challenges affect the SDCA students? 3) How does resilience emerge as a grassroots coping strategy of SDCA students in dealing with the effects of Covid-19 pandemic?

Methodology

Through the interviews conducted with the selected SDCA students coming from Education, Pharmacy, AB Communication, Nursing, and Tourism Management, their stories clearly reflect real life struggles, rooted from the serious effects caused by the Covid-19 pandemic. To express the concept, Figure 1 illustrates the interplay of the variables presented in input-environment-output (IEO) model by Astin (1984).

Input. The traditional Indians bring stability in their society by preserving their culture. Majority are farmers who harvest and sell grain and trade it for food in the village. For their personal consumption, Rukmani maintains a fruit and vegetable patch. Traditional Indians depends upon nature: the rain, rice and land. Most of them believe in superstitions. They expect their sons to continue their family's long tradition of tilling the land, living in extended families, and adhering to Hindu traditions. This shows the Indian traditional mindset.

Environment. The SDCA students' stories center on the effects of Covid-19 pandemic and how they survived it. There were sudden policies, restrictions, and healthy protocols implemented to limit people's movements and fight the spread of the virus.

Output. Despite the threat of Covid-19 pandemic, the SDCA students accept the situation as an inevitable event. This is a philosophy of resilience. The way they were able to cling to each other and maintain a healthy relationship despite the stressful events in their environment, makes them successfully adapt and cope with the demands of the human transformation.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework

Results and Discussion

The SDCA students although most of them belong to well-off families, also experienced struggle and serious effect, most of them need to work while studying (40%), others sell online (20%), while others were able to create advocacy for them to spend their time meaningfully (20%). Although one student (20%) lost her sister due to Covid-19, but this did not discourage him to stop his studies, but he was able to accept the situation and become fully aware on how to adjust and move on in life by making himself occupied to video streaming. Hope is seen as a resiliency factor by some researchers, which is a positive attitude toward life and the ability to have optimistic views (Moorey & Greer, 1989; Strang & Strang, 2001; Sawatzky et al., 2009). This is what mostly seen from the SDCA students.

A global movement calling for a new paradigm of learning for the twenty-first century has emerged around the world. Fadel (2015) offers a complete framework for the 21st century education, and one of the dimensions about character qualities is resilience. In the Philippines, 21st century skills are core to the K to 12 curricula. The curriculum also places an emphasis on resilience as one of the significant 21st century skills. This is the Philippine education realizing that an important goal of education is to develop people who can respond to challenges and setbacks.

If resilience is one of the significant skills that 21st century learners should develop, then various pandemic narratives at SDCA should be considered, which meaningfully conveys the theme of resilience along with the threats of social and personal transformation. What we should learn from the Filipino values is that Filipinos live more in the heart than in their mind, the heart that can never touch or influence them, especially their religion or culture (Ang et al., 2021; Cleofas, 2021).

The strong message in this research, however, is that threats, stress, problems or failures exist in all humans, regardless of age or status in life. It is how we deal with it for us to survive. As the great Confucius says, *'Our greatest glory is not in never falling, but in rising every time we fall'*. And through literature, educators can better cultivate the grassroots values of Resilience to prepare students to cope with real life stressing experiences and be able to achieve positive outcomes. Resilience is a personal strength that enables each of our own life journeys and is the growth capacity, which enables survival throughout human history.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Since the growing concern and urgency of the present curriculum is to equip students with 21st century skills, such as resilience, this is where literature or humanities fit in. This would then be particularly significant to the teachers and students.

Covid-19 pandemic narratives give teachers opportunities to make every literature classes significant by identifying the valuable themes that underlie each text. Learning from the grassroots values of a literary text such as the SDCA students, teachers engage the innate resilience and well-being of their students. Thus, teaching becomes much more natural, meaningful and enjoyable.

With an identified theme related to skills or values from a literary text such as the SDCA students' pandemic narratives, it clearly tells us that we really care and believe in to our nation's

most precious resource: our students, our children. We are not only facilitating students' healthy development and successful learning, but we are also fostering social transformation from the inside out, cultivating the caring and creative citizens who will be vital in the twenty-first century.

References

- Ang, W. H. D., Shorey, S., Lopez, V., Chew, H. S. J., & Lau, Y. (2021). Generation Z undergraduate students' resilience during the COVID-19 pandemic: a qualitative study. *Current Psychology*, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-021-01830-4>
- Astin, A. W. (1984). Student involvement: A developmental theory for higher education. *Journal of College Student Personnel*, 25(4), 297-308. http://chawkinson.pbworks.com/w/file/fetch/122997693/Student_Involvement_A_Development_Theory_for_Highe.pdf
- Cleofas, J. V. (2021). Life interruptions, learnings and hopes among Filipino college students during COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Loss and Trauma*, 26(6), 552-560. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15325024.2020.1846443>
- Fadel, C. (2015). *Redesigning the curriculum for a 21st century education*. Center for Curriculum Redesign. <https://curriculumredesign.org/wp-content/uploads/CCR-FoundationalPaper-Updated-Jan2016.pdf>
- Moorey, S., & Greer, S. (1989). Adjuvant Psychological Therapy: A cognitive behavioural treatment for patients with cancer. *Behavioural and Cognitive Psychotherapy*, 17(2), 177-190. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0141347300016141>
- Sawatzky, J. A. V., Enns, C. L., Ashcroft, T. J., Davis, P. L., & Harder, B. N. (2009). Teaching excellence in nursing education: A caring framework. *Journal of Professional Nursing*, 25(5), 260-266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.profnurs.2009.01.017>
- Strang, S., & Strang, P. (2001). Spiritual thoughts, coping and 'sense of coherence' in brain tumour patients and their spouses. *Palliative Medicine*, 15(2), 127-134. <https://doi.org/10.1191/026921601670322085>
- Teodoro, L. V. (2020, July 9). *Philippine education in crisis*. BusinessWorld. <https://www.bworldonline.com/philippine-education-in-crisis/>